

PHILOSOPHICAL SCIENCES

INFOCOMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES AS A FACTOR OF GLOBAL SYSTEM FORMATION

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ABSTRACT

The article reveals the role of info-communication technologies as one of the most important factors of modern global system formation. The article analyzes the prerequisites and conditions of this process, as well as its impact on various spheres of modern society. The article substantiates the paradigmatic importance of information and communication technologies in the transformation of structural elements and processes of modern civilization functioning.

Keywords: system of info-communication technologies, civilization, global system formation, paradigm factor, infoecological space.

The intensive process of formation of the global (planet-wide) civilization system, which began in the second half of the XIX century, entered a qualitatively new stage in the 80s of the XX century. It was connected with the emergence and subsequent formation of the information society. The active introduction of information and communication technologies in all spheres of society has significantly strengthened the processes of global integration. This was manifested, firstly, in the qualitative increase in the speed of their spread. Secondly, internationalization has covered new spheres of economy and social life in general, which previously traditionally remained relatively stable and unchanged (national standards of production, features of management technologies, family and domestic life, lifestyle, features of national moral and cultural values, etc.).

In order to clarify the qualitative specifics of the modern stage of formation of a unified system of human civilization, it is necessary to identify the most important factors that condition the origin and development of this process in concrete-historical conditions.

Initially, the establishment of links between different territories was associated with the emergence and development of trade, which, in turn, was possible in the presence of a certain level of production. The appeared surplus product created an objective opportunity for the emergence of stable relations on the exchange of goods between different countries and peoples. However, despite the initial commonality and similarity of tools of labor in different territories occupied by human civilization, the relatively low level of labor productivity and the minimum amount of surplus product conditioned the formation of relatively unstable, easily disappearing relations between different countries and peoples.

The next important stage in the formation of a unified system of human civilization dates back to the era of the great geographical discoveries. During this period, firstly, scientific geographical ideas about the Earth as a whole were formed. Secondly, stable economic ties were established between separate parts of the world and the system of world trade began to form.

Thirdly, the initial accumulation of capital took place, which was the most important prerequisite for the unfolding of the Industrial Revolution. The unfolding of these processes leads by the mid-19th century to a leapfrog expansion of the real human perception of the true unity of world civilization, to the actual transcendence of existing not only local but also national-state boundaries.

In the second half of the twentieth century, there are two more fundamentally important factors that ensure the further development of system formation processes on a global scale.

In this specific-historical period, firstly, the global system of production, distribution, exchange and consumption of energy resources, primarily hydrocarbon resources, is formed and confirmed in its basic parameters. In addition, the corresponding global systems of transportation and processing, financial institutions serving these processes and political mechanisms ensuring their sustainability were also formalized.

Secondly, in the second half of the XX century, the world began to observe the processes that were later called the scientific and technological revolution. The radical qualitative transformation of the productive forces of the entire human society on the basis of the merger of revolutions in science and technology (with the leading role of science) leads to an unprecedented intensity of the exchange of scientific and technical achievements, the active development of common standards, regulations, methods of communication in this component of human civilization. Such a leap in the development of science and technology objectively require for their normal functioning the corresponding intensity of exchange between different countries in these components of human civilization. The social need arising in this framework simultaneously creates corresponding opportunities for its own realization. Due to the action of these factors, the global system formation quickly acquires new powerful sources of its own development.

This becomes evident in just two decades, when in the 80s of the XX the information society emerges, begins to function and develop. The changes taking place

in various spheres of society gradually unfold inherent characteristics that had not been previously manifested in the history of mankind. In addition, previously non-existent structural components appear and evolve. In our opinion, the most important of them in this aspect is the system of information and communication technologies, which naturally emerges as a result of the development of the universal cognitive process.

In our opinion, the formation and development of the system of info-communication technologies can be characterized and further investigated on the following essential grounds:

- 1) by the scale of dissemination;
- 2) by levels of system organization;
- 3) by the changes introduced into the construction of social space;
- 4) by the transformation of processes of social time passing.

Obviously, the above-mentioned bases are not absolutely isolated and independent of each other; they are interrelated with necessity. On their basis, it becomes possible to fix the corresponding stages of evolution of the system under consideration.

The characterization of the development of information and communication technologies, made on the basis of the first two bases, describes their formation on their own basis; this system of technologies is considered in these cases as relatively isolated. In this sense, these processes appear to be relatively simple. They describe mainly quantitative parameters of the processes and stages of development of the information and communication technology system. The third and fourth bases for analysis appear to be much more complex and developed, since within their framework it is necessary to identify stages of significant impact on the fundamental structures of society as a whole.

Let us try to briefly characterize the formation of the structure of information and communication technologies according to the above-mentioned parameters.

At the present stage of development, the local, regional, state, interstate and global levels are clearly defined by the scale of spread of the info-communication technologies system. Since this allocation seems rather obvious to us, it is not reasonable to specifically analyze the properties and features of each of them within the framework of this small work. However, it is necessary, in our opinion, to note that the highlighted levels characterize a sufficiently formed and structured system. In reality, the processes of evolution of information and communication technologies, their distribution and formalization into a single complex occurred in a non-linear manner.

Classifying the development of info-communication technologies by levels of system organization, one can clearly fix the stages of their functioning in the form of unrelated personal computers, local networks and global network. It is necessary to keep in mind that the selected periods are characterized not only by different hardware components, ways and scales of their integration, appearance of corresponding software, but also by the formation of specific system algorithms of their construction. And the latter turn out to be the most

dynamic component. For example, just a few years after the beginning of the processes of active formation of computer networks, it was possible to record the history of their emergence with the allocation of specific stages of architecture development, significantly different from each other: multi-terminal, file-server, client-server, peer-to-peer, cloud. [1]. It is the evolution of the latter that turns out to be the factor that leads at the present stage to the empirically fixed impact of the virtual environment on the structure and properties of the surrounding material world.

Already at the end of the twentieth century there were predictions about such an increasing role of computers in the life of mankind. [2, p. 15 – 20]. However, now it is possible to observe changes in the basic structures of human civilization. Let us try to briefly record them.

Procedures, norms and algorithms, developed in the process of functioning of the system of information and communication technologies, begin to affect the already existing spheres of human society (economic, social, political and spiritual), obviously changing their essential characteristics.

The development of the system of info-communication technologies also affects the deeper foundations of human civilization.

There is an obvious transformation of social space. This process began with the widespread use of personal computers, which required changes at the level of microspace. At the present stage, the transformation of the global space of mankind is obvious. For example, the geopolitical map of the world can be described on the basis of the location, number and power of info-communication centers. In a sense, the Internet nodes are becoming the centers of civilization growth.

The info-communication system is gradually changing social time as well. Initially, it affected only people professionally engaged in this sphere - their lives were synchronized in accordance with the needs of this system. However, already now information and communication algorithms have changed the real dynamics of social time and its subjective perception by billions of people. The importance of real and virtual time in the life of society is gradually changing in favor of the latter.

One can say that the algorithms of the info-communication system "go" beyond its limits. They form a virtual reality, complex in its structure, in which elements traditionally distinguished in objective reality (economic, social, political, spiritual) gradually emerge. There is a certain "doubling" of civilization.

As a result, at least three major aspects of the system-forming impact of info-communication technologies on human civilization as a whole can be distinguished.

First, information and communication technologies do not simply affect and influence all structural components of the human civilization system - economic, social, political and spiritual - without exception, but qualitatively change them. Moreover, these technologies are not just actively, massively and systematically used in these spheres as a necessary but auxiliary component, but also begin to define common

ideals, norms, rules and procedures of ongoing and objectively required transformations.

Secondly, the system of information and communication technologies existing in modern conditions is obviously global in the full and precise sense of the word. It covers all countries of the world regardless of their level of development. If in the era of the scientific and technological revolution the subjects and main consumers of its results were the most developed countries, and the rest could use (to a greater or lesser extent) only the products and technologies provided by these countries, now the situation is significantly different. The products of the sphere of information and communication technologies are directly available to the mass consumer almost irrespective of the level of income, education, cultural and other traditions.

Thirdly, the previously functioning system-forming factors for the world civilization set only the general direction of transformations, determined only ultimately changes in all spheres of human society. Information and communication technologies realize this function directly. They form the basic norms, procedures, ways and means of receiving, processing, storing, transmitting, exchanging (distributing) and consuming (using) information. As a result, a system of global information communication emerges, which largely levels economic, cultural and educational, national-historical, moral and ethical, religious, political, social and other differences. A certain new material-virtual sphere with its own economic, social, political and spiritual characteristics is formed and begins to evolve independently, encompassing and actively changing virtually all of humanity.

Thus, information and communication technologies are not just present as an independent element of world civilization. They are beginning to increasingly transform the other components of this system in accordance with their own ideals and norms of functioning and development, which are constantly being formed. This system is actively unfolding in the economic sphere of society as its most dynamically devel-

oping component and as a factor transforming other elements of the global economic system. In addition, these technologies are beginning to increasingly determine the functioning of the processes occurring in the political system of modern society. Finally, information and communication technologies are already in many ways shaping the new social structure of society. Setting certain requirements to a person and making noticeable changes in living conditions, the system of info-communication technologies actively forms, in accordance with them, large social groups and strata characterized by similar sizes and ways of income generation, educational level, style of thinking, similar vocabulary, norms of behavior, value orientations, lifestyle in general [3, p. 13]. Moreover, at the current stage of civilizational evolution, the development of the system of info-communication technologies leads to the emergence and formation of a special ecological space (infoecological space), which is required for its normal functioning [4, p. 54 – 55].

Based on the above, we can conclude that information and communication technologies are beginning to act as a *system-forming factor of special significance, paradigmatic* in terms of the results of its impact on the essential characteristics of all structures of the human society system without exception.

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